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ODDIY LOVIYA TURI BOSHLANG‘ICH MANBALARI VA F₁, F₂ DURAGAYLARIDA URUG‘ TARKIBIDAGI ERKIN AMINOKISLOTALAR MIQDORI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada oddiy loviya turining mahalliy va xorijiy navlari, ulardan olingan F₁-F₂ duragaylarining urug‘ida aminokislotalar miqdori natijalari tahlil qilinganda, ota-ona manbalardan Belaya fasol navida boshqa navlarga nisbatan yuqori ko‘rsatkichlarni, ya‘ni, asparagin kislota (1,047 mg/g), glutamin (8,47 mg/g), treonin (1,39 mg/g), alanin (7,96 mg/g), metionin (1,00 mg/g), gistidin (6,38 mg/g) miqdorining yuqori ekanligi, F₁ duragaylaridan glitsin (0,993 mg/g), alanin (6,393 mg/g), prolin (1,66 mg/g), sistein (2,167), F₂ duragaylarda alanin (7,170 mg/g), fenilalanin (3,976 mg/g) erkin aminokislotlar miqdori yuqori bo‘lishi qayd etildi.

Kalit so‘zlar: oddiy loviya, duragay, nav, oqsil, aminokislota, alanin, gistidin, valin, treonin.

Abstract. In this article, when analyzing the results of amino acid content in the seeds of local and foreign varieties of common bean and their F₁-F₂, hybrids, it was found that among the parental sources, the “Belaya fasol” variety showed higher values compared to other varieties. Specifically, it had higher levels of aspartic acid (1.047 mg/g), glutamine (8.47 mg/g), threonine (1.39 mg/g), alanine (7.96 mg/g), methionine (1.00 mg/g), and histidine (6.38 mg/g). Among the F₁ hybrids, higher amounts of glycine (0.993 mg/g), alanine (6.393 mg/g), proline (1.66 mg/g), and cysteine (2.167 mg/g) were recorded, while in the F₂ hybrids, increased levels of alanine (7.170 mg/g) and phenylalanine (3.976 mg/g) of free amino acids were observed.

Keywords: common bean, hybrid, variety, protein, amino acid, alanine, histidine, valine, threonine.

Kirish. Olimlar tomonidan oddiy loviya o‘simligining xo‘jalik, morfofenologik, molekulyar-genetik va ozuqaviy qiymati yuqori bo‘lgan elita navlarini yaratishga qaratilgan zamonaviy uslublardan foydalanib ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilgan [2].

Oddiy loviya o‘simligining abiotik stresslarga ko‘proq bardoshli genotiplarining rivojlanishida ular ildizlarining tarqalish xususiyatining yuqori bo‘lishi ahamiyatli ekanligi 6 ta boshlang‘ich manbalar va 30 ta F₁ duragaylarda ildiz tarqalishida geterozis holatining paydo bo‘lishiga qaratilgan. Natijada ildizlarda geterozisning kuzatilmaganligi gen guruhlari o‘rtasidagi qarindoshlik darajasi, shuningdek, ba‘zi o‘zaro epistatik ta’sirlar bilan izohlangan [5].

Shuningdek tepariy loviyasi issiq va quruq iqlim sharoitiga moslashgan. Bu turdan genetika va molekulyar biologiya sohasida to‘liq foydalanilmagan. So‘nggi yillarda tepariy loviyasi ustida genetik tadqiqotlar ko‘plab amalga oshirilmogda [3, 4]. Vronska L. V., Demyd A. Ye. [7] olib borgan tadqiqotlarida oddiy loviya o‘simligi 5 xil oq urug‘li namunalarning aminokislota tarkibi xromatografiya usulida o‘rganilganda aspartat va glutamin kislota, glitsin, valin, tirozin, leysin va boshqa aminokislotalar aniqlangan. [1].

Tadqiqot obyekti va usuli. Tadqiqot obyekti sifatida oddiy loviya turiga mansub Beybi Lima, Vir, Belaya fasol, Kalipso krasnaya, Solnishko, Ravot navlari va F₁-F₂ duragaylaridan foydalanildi. Erkin aminokislotalarning feniltiokarbomail (FTK) bilan hosilasi (birikmasi) yuqori samarali suyuqlik xromatografiya (YuSSX) tahlili Steven, Cohen Daviel [6] usulida amalga oshirildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari. O‘rganilgan 6 ta loviya navlarida Belaya fasol navida boshqa navlarga nisbatan yuqori ko‘rsatkichlarni, ya‘ni, asparagin kislota (1,047mg/g), glutamin (8,479 mg/g), treonin (1,399479 mg/g), alanin (7,96 mg/g), metionin (1,0077 mg/g), gistidin (6,38 mg/g), izoleysin (0,30 mg/g), leysin (0,664 mg/g), triptofan (0,669 mg/g), fenilalanin (0,456 mg/g), lizin (0,584 mg/g), Kalipso navida asparagin (1,787 mg/g), arginin (0,941 mg/g), prolin (1,24 mg/g), valin (0,80), Vir navida glutamin kislota (2,56 mg/g) va tirozin (2,021 mg/g), Ravot navida serin (1,294 mg/g), glitsin (0,760 mg/g) va sistein (2,08 mg/g) kabi erkin aminokislotalar miqdori yuqori ekanligi aniqlandi.

F₁ Kalipso krasnaya x Beybi Lima kombinatsiyasida glitsin (0,993861 mg/g), alanin (6,3931 mg/g), prolin (1,66 mg/g), valin (0,856 mg/g), leysin (0,468 mg/g), va F₁ Kalipso krasnaya x Solnishko kombinatsiyasida asparagin (1,689 mg/g), arginin (0,92 mg/g), gistidin (5,83 mg/g) erkin aminokislotalar miqdori boshqa duragay kombinatsiyalarga nisbatan yuqori bo‘lishi kuzatildi.

F₂ o‘simliklarida biokimyoviy tahlil natijalari shuni ko‘rsatdiki, erkin aminokislotalar miqdori Beybi Lima navi ishtirok etgan F₂ kombinatsiyalarida ham keyingi avlodlarda o‘z kuchini saqlab qolganini ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Jumladan, F₂ Beybi Lima x Kalipso krasnaya kombinatsiyasida asparagin kislota (0,989 mg/g), serin (1,18 mg/g), tirozin (1,5093 mg/g), lizin (0,411 mg/g), glitsin (1,134801 mg/g), asparagin (2,2755 mg/g), treonin (1,62 mg/g), arginin (0,910 mg/g), alanin (7,170269 mg/g), prolin (1,67 mg/g), fenilalanin (3,97 mg/g) erkin aminokislotalar miqdori boshqa F₂ o‘simliklariga nisbatan yuqori bo‘lishi qayd etildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko‘rsatdiki, oddiy loviya navlari va F₁-F₂ o‘simliklari urug‘i tarkibidagi erkin aminokislotalar miqdori tahlil qilinganda, Beybi Lima navi bilan chatishtirib olingan F₁-F₂ o‘simlik kombinatsiyalarida

yuqori ko‘rsatkichlar aniqlandi hamda ushbu kombinatsiyalar genetik-seleksion tadqiqotlarda irsiy boyitilgan oila, tizma va navlar yaratishda qimmatli manba bo‘la oladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Ángel Ramón Flores-Sosa, Elia Nora Aquino-Bolaños Variation in protein and amino acids content among landraces of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). // Emirates Journal of Food and Agriculture. 2020. - P. 750-760.
2. Pietro Sica, Francesco Scariolo, Aline Galvao Agronomic Performances and Seed Nutraceutical Properties to Exploit Neglected Genetic Resources of *Common Beans* Grown by Organic Farming in Two Contrasting Environments // Front. Plant Sci. 2021. Volume 12. -P. 1-24.
3. Rahman Sk.M., Aniszewski T. Ladybird beetles *Adalia bipunctata* L. Interaction with legume bean *Phaseolus* species is dependent on life needs // Malaysian Applied Biology. 2014. - P. 111-118.
4. Sergio Cruz, Juan Lobaton, Milan O. Urban Interspecific common bean population derived from *Phaseolus acutifolius* using a bridging genotype demonstrate useful adaptation to heat tolerance // Front. Plant Sci. 2023. Volume 14. - P. 1-15.
5. Sibila Grigolo, Rita Carolina de Melo, Heterosis for the root distribution trait in common bean // Agronomy journal, 2021. Volume 43, -P. 44-48.
6. Vronska L.V., Demyd A.Ye. Amino acid profile of *Phaseolus vulgaris* pods and dry extract prepared of them. // Farmasevtichniy chasopis. 2019. -P. 40-48.